

WRAPTOR BAMBOO TRUSSES: QUANTIFYING THE IMPACT OF CULM GEOMETRY VARIATION ON BENDING PERFORMANCE

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Keywords: Natural Materials, Composite Trusses, Bamboo

ABSTRACT

Full culm bamboo is a natural material which could be used as the primary constituent as elements in efficient truss geometries that could subsequently be used to assemble larger hierarchical spaceframes. Using bamboo in such structures removes limitations on bamboo constructions imposed by the natural size and shape of the grown plant that cannot be controlled. Traditional truss manufacturing methods are unsuitable for bamboo as it is comprised of longitudinally aligned fibres prone to splitting, thus the Wrapped Tow Reinforced (WrapToR) truss manufacturing process, originally developed for fibre reinforced polymers, is adapted here. WrapToR produces composite material trusses via winding a continuous composite tow around pultruded tubes mounted on a mandrel. If bamboo were to be substituted for the pultruded tubes, the innate geometric variation between and within bamboo culms will cause challenges in truss winding and performance prediction of WrapToR trusses. A non-concentric circle culm model of bamboo culms is developed here to measure and represent this geometry variation. This method operates at a middle fidelity between simpler prismatic estimations of shape and higher fidelity measurements of the full 3D geometry. It uses physical measurements from a bespoke rig to estimate circular cross sections of a culm at regular length intervals, which are then lofted into a full culm. These models are then used to provide geometry responsive path planning for the winding machine, and are also used within finite element analysis to provide estimates for individual culm bending performance and full WrapToR truss performance. The FEA models are then validated against data gathered from mechanical testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

An ever increasing focus on the development of sustainable construction methods has motivated research into the use of bamboo as an alternative material in buildings and infrastructure. Historically, bamboo was widely used for construction throughout its naturally occurring range, but today it is usually overlooked in favour of more common materials such as concrete, steel, masonry, and timber [1]. The primary advantage of using bamboo is that it has mechanical properties competitive with timbers, whilst having a faster growth rate, reaching maturity within 3-5 years [1,2]. Faster replenishment time of construction material provides environmental benefits such as lower levels of deforestation, as less land is required to grow the same amount of material [2]. These factors have recently led to a resurgence in research into the use of bamboo and its usage has been demonstrated in a variety of showcase applications [2,3,4].

The stalk or 'culm' of the Bamboo plant can be used directly 'as harvested' as tubular beam like elements, or they can be split down into smaller segments and reformed into composites to allow more geometrical freedom. Using the full culm as a beam can be advantageous, allowing for the utilisation of the efficient natural structure of bamboo as a thin walled, hollow tube comprised of longitudinally oriented fibres. The limitation of using full culm bamboo is that the size and shape of what can be built are limited by the size of culm that can be grown. The material properties of bamboo, while impressive for natural materials, are also lower than conventional construction materials such as steel, further reducing what applications that it is suitable for.

The efficient structure of bamboo culms can be leveraged by using them as members in truss or space frame structures. Trusses take advantage of highly non-linear structural scaling laws by putting small amounts of material into localised members which are spaced far away from each other, allowing them to balance large forces and bending moments with minimal stress. These members are also loaded axially which suits the structure of full culms. However, there is still a limit on the size, stiffness, and strength of the individual elements of these trusses stemming from the growth size limitations of the culm. In order to make larger and more highly loaded structures, one promising approach is the use of hierarchical space frames (HSFs), where the beam like members of the larger truss or spaceframe are themselves made from trusses. These truss beams could be made from longitudinally aligned bamboo culms that are held apart from each other by some form of shear web structure. These truss beams would have much higher second moment of area, and therefore stiffness and strength, than the culms on their own, and would therefore provide a way around the limitations on size and shape imposed by natural growth. These truss beams could then be connected together to form HSFs with a significant amount of design freedom with regards to size, geometry, and load carrying capacity. The key enabling element to this concept of bamboo based HSFs is the ability to quickly and efficiently manufacture truss beams from bamboo culms.

1.1 Wrapped Tow Reinforced Composite Trusses and Space Frames.

Similar work on attempting to fully utilise impressive properties of structures comprised of longitudinally oriented fibres has been conducted for the Wrapped Tow Reinforced (WrapToR) method which produce efficient truss structures from advanced composite materials such as carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) or glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP). WrapToR is an adapted form of filament winding, where composite pultruded tubes are mounted on a rotating mandrel where a single wetted composite tow is wound around the mounted pultruded tubes. The wetted composite co-cures to the surface of the pultrusion and forms a rigid truss beam such as the one shown in Figure 1. Because the WrapToR process only utilises adhesive co-curing and no physical fasteners, stress concentrations forming at fastener holes that propagate into large cracks are not seen in WrapToR trusses. WrapToR minimises the complexity of composite assembly, offering a simple, automated method of producing composite trusses.

Figure 1: Wrapped Tow Reinforced truss.

The structural performance of WrapToR trusses has to date mostly been explored within the context of lightweight, high performance aerospace structures made from carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) [5,6], where it has shown exceptional performance. For example, outperforming unidirectional pultruded carbon fibre reinforced polymer tubes of a similar mass in a three-point bending test by 1006% in terms of stiffness and 181% in terms of maximum load at failure. WrapToR achieves this performance through its geometry by spacing the chord members far from the centre of the truss, maximising second moment of area, and therefore bending rigidity, for the same mass. The orientations of the fibres for both the chord members are also aligned in the axial direction for each member, which is the optimal direction

for this type of structure, which helps to get the most of the material used. Furthermore, the WrapToR method imparts a twist to the tow during winding in order to change the tow's shape from a thin ribbon into a circular cross section, increasing the buckling resistance of the wound shear members and the load carrying capacity of the truss beam [6]. Hierarchical space frames made from CFRP WrapToR truss beams have been previously explored using numerical modelling and structural optimisation [7].

1.2 Bamboo WrapToR HSFs: Potential and Challenges

The fundamental geometric advantages provided by WrapToR truss beams should be transferable to natural materials, given the top-level similarities in the structure of bamboo and pultruded composite tubes. A bamboo WrapToR HSF carries multiple advantages over using only a bamboo culm as a singular beam member. Because the truss beam geometry significantly increases the stiffness and strength of the bamboo material, while also loading the culm in a way which is very well suited to its inherent structural design, WrapToR HSFs can help mitigate the discrepancy in material properties between bamboo and other construction materials, especially when considered in a mass normalised manner. Another potential advantage of WrapToR bamboo HSFs would be the fundamental scalability of the design. If a comprehensive method of joining trusses together is developed, trusses can be assembled end to end allowing truss beam to be lengthened. This modular approach eliminates the issue that full culm bamboo structures are limited by the size and shape that they can be grown at. The WrapToR method also has advantages over conventional trusses as it is a simple, rapid and automated production method. In conventional truss structures many individual smaller elements must be carefully manufactured and then carefully assembled, a process which typically carries a high time and labour cost. In contrast, a WrapToR beam is composed of only 4 parts, the three chord members and the continuously wound shear web. A full truss winding can be carried out quickly by an automated machine and then left to cure [8].

However, significant challenges, particularly the geometric variation of bamboo culms, must be addressed before bamboo can be effectively used in WrapToR trusses. Geometric variation, both between different culms and across individual culms is a challenge that has to be solved to get the most performance out of bamboo in a WrapToR truss. As with all natural materials, geometric variation occurs as part of the growth process and cannot be fully predicted, controlled or prevented. In other natural materials that are more commonly used, for example timber, geometric variation is handled via sawing logs down into standardised and regularly shaped sections. Conventional sawing or machining processes are less useful for bamboo because the structure of bamboo culms is predominately a thin-walled tube, so the size of solid members than can be cut out of them are small.

Geometric changes such as changes in tube diameter and wall thickness; the number and position of nodes; or naturally occurring bends in the material will all have some effect on the overall stiffness and load bearing capacity of the culm. Furthermore, variation will also cause difficulty in the winding process for WrapToR trusses. The WrapToR winding process is controlled via G-code and open-loop control of the motors, hence the machine is 'blind' to the mandrel and the chord's mounted positions [8]. This means that the quality and accuracy of the winding is determined by the initial position of the chord members. In a regular composite pultrusion WrapToR truss the chord members are prismatic, and such the winding path can be easily calculated through simple trigonometry because the points of contact between the shear members and chord members are consistently placed. In WrapToR trusses with bamboo chord members path calculation is not trivial as the positions of the chord member and shear member connections change, dependent on the unique variation of the bamboo culm used. Furthermore, any combination of three bamboo culms each with their own variation can make manufacture difficult. An illustration of the challenge is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Winding challenges due to geometric variation

A method of capturing and representing the geometry of the culm that incorporates geometric variation will aid in addressing these challenges. Such a method should help in understanding the effects of variation on culm structural performance and allow for more precise winding within the WrapToR manufacturing process.

A simple method of culm representation is presented in the ISO standard for testing bamboo culm performance, namely BS ISO 22157. This approach takes two perpendicular measurements of culm width from an area in between two nodes, then assume a thin-walled tube with a diameter equal to the average of the two measurements [9]. This approximation does not effectively represent the geometry in a manner that would allow for the winding challenges depicted in Figure 2 to be solved, thus a higher fidelity model is required here. Higher fidelity approaches have been considered in other work, for example the use of a laser scanner to capture the full three dimensional outer geometry of bamboo culms, which were used within the computer aided design of a bamboo structure [10]. While this method captures the surface geometry in full, allowing for all the required analysis to be undertaken, it requires specialist equipment such as a full-field 3D laser scanner and actuating robotic arm control [10], and takes significant time to capture high quality scans [11]. Furthermore, these scans tend to be computationally expensive to use in analysis due to the large size of data sets created.

In order to better balance the fidelity of the geometry representation against the amount of effort required to create and use it, this work introduces a non-concentric circle culm model for bamboo culm geometries that sits at an intermediate fidelity. It is intended to be accurate enough to capture the first order impact of the geometry while also being significantly easier and faster to measure than a full laser scan, while also producing much smaller data sets that are easier to use within numerical modelling. The following section details how the non-concentric circle culm model measures and captures the geometry of bamboo culms. We then compare finite element analysis models, produced from the captured geometry to physical bending tests conducted on the scanned culms to assess the effectiveness of the models and to determine whether non-concentric circle based models can predict performance better than simple prismatic models. We then conduct the same study on manufactured trusses to determine its effectiveness for modelling the bending performance of WrapToR truss beams made with the measured bamboo culms.

2 NON-CONCENTRIC CIRCLE CULM MODEL

In the non-concentric circle culm model, the cross section of the culm at any point along its length is approximated as a circle, with the culm itself being composed of many linked circles of various sizes and positions. The centres of these circles are not assumed to be colinear however, instead the effective centre of each circle is measured in three-dimensional space, allowing for curvature and other discontinuities along the length of the culm. Therefore, this approach is able to capture the diameter changes and lack of straightness that are typical of bamboo culms. The calculated circles are lofted together to produce the model of the culm surface.

The bespoke rig used to take the surface measurements is shown in Figure 3. This rig is comprised of five different potentiometers and a sliding mount to hold the culm at a fixed reference location. In this rig physical potentiometers are used although precision single point laser distance sensors may also be appropriate. As shown in Figure 3, four potentiometers (5V Gefran PY2-50, Gefran) are mounted on a circular frame at the centre of the rig. Because the positions of each of the four potentiometers is fixed and known, this establishes a reference area where the measurements taken can be related to a cartesian position within the area, where the centre is taken to be the origin. The fifth potentiometer is a CD50S string potentiometer which records the longitudinal position of the culm. An Arduino control board was used which provided a resolution of 0.05 mm with the four surface measurement potentiometers and a resolution of 1 mm for the string potentiometer. This provides measurements for 1000 cross sections for a 1 m culm. The mounted culm is passed through the potentiometers using the slider, and measurements are taken from each. For each cross section, five different values are obtained, four relate to the surface distance from the potentiometer mount and one value for the longitudinal position of that particular cross section along the culm.

Figure 3: Bespoke culm measurement rig.

Each of the four surface measurements are related to a cartesian coordinate within a reference area defined by the known position of the potentiometers as shown in Figure 4. Three of the four coordinates calculated are substituted into the set of simultaneous equations shown in Equation 1 to define the cross section of the culm as a circle with the radius, r , and the centre of the circle (a, b).

$$\begin{aligned} (x1 - a)^2 + (y1 - b)^2 &= r^2 \\ (x2 - a)^2 + (y2 - b)^2 &= r^2 \\ (x3 - a)^2 + (y3 - b)^2 &= r^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

This process is repeated four times for each possible set of three coordinates. The final circle is calculated as the averaged from each circle produced using Equation 1. The averaged circle calculated from four measurements are taken rather than the minimum three as it is possible that certain surface features like divots are overrepresented and skew the resulting model when only three measurements are used. To create the external surface model of the culm as shown in Figure 5, the centre of each circle is placed at its calculated position in all three dimensions. A point cloud is then generated from these stacked circles by seeding a fixed number of points around the circumference of each circle.

Figure 4: Representation of how measurements are taken for non-concentric circle culm model

Figure 5: Top: progression from real culm to NCCM point cloud, to FEA mesh. Bottom: Comparison of NCCM model of a culm to the equivalent prismatic model

3 INDIVIDUAL CULM FEA MODELS AND VALIDATION

After using the non-concentric circle culm model to produce a point cloud that is representative of the culm geometry, the point clouds are then converted into Abaqus finite element analysis models using an automated process. A bespoke Matlab code is used to write the coordinates of the point clouds into an Abaqus input file. The meshes generated directly from the point cloud produce FEA models with high element numbers, in the order of millions, and so mesh convergence analysis was carried out to determine how much the mesh can be reduced without impacting the results of the model. This found that removing every 7th cross section and limiting the number of seeded surface points to 16 was suitable. The progression of this process and the reduced mesh size for the FEA models are shown in

Figure 5

S4R shell elements were used to model the bamboo culm. Shell elements were chosen due to the desire to strike a balance between fidelity and computation time, where shell elements are significantly less expensive than brick elements in FEA. These element types are commonly used for the modelling of composite parts and as such it is sensible to use them in a ‘composite like’ material such as bamboo. It is not expected that the transverse properties of the structure will carry significant effects, especially in the load cases being tested and as such this element choice is justified. It is possible for a variety of load cases to be simulated, of particular interest has been the prediction of deflections under three-point and four-point bending loads as a means to validate the produced models against mechanical tests.

Each generated model possesses the same material properties and element types. The material properties used in the FEA models are taken from material testing done on the same batch of bamboo culms used in the validation experiments, and were tested in accordance with BS ISO 22157. The wall thickness of each bamboo culm was calculated by first determining the density of that particular culm, by measuring the mass and volume of smaller samples cut from the ends of the culm. By measuring the mass of the whole culm the volume can be calculated which can be used to determine an average wall thickness value given that the length of the culm and outer diameter are known.

3.1 FEA Model Validation

To verify the effectiveness of finite element analysis models, mechanical testing was conducted on bamboo culms of various lengths in three-point bending. In these tests the culm is suspended on two rollers and bending displacements of 20mm were imposed on each culm at the midspan point. A single measurement of displacement was taken at the lower surface on the midpoint of the culm using a

potentiometer. Moso Bamboo, with diameters 22mm to 26mm were used as these are the desired culms to be used in future WrapToR trusses. Three lengths of culm were used, 750mm, 875mm and 1000mm, to ensure that the models are valid for a range of lengths.

For each bamboo culm tested for model validation two FEA models were produced, one which uses geometry generated though the non-concentric circle culm model and the other which uses a prismatic tube geometry where the diameter has been measured in accordance with BS ISO 22157. This comparison has been made to determine if the using the scanned geometry to generate FEA models is advantageous for modelling bending behaviour for bamboo culms rather than using the established, existing methodology.

Figure 6 shows the results from 3-point testing compared to the results predicted by the non-concentric circle based FEA model and the prismatic tube FEA model. Both models are able to predict the culm's response reasonably well as demonstrated by the agreement between the three lines. The calculated bending stiffness of the culms based on the initial linear region of the deflections from both the models and experiments are shown in Figure 7. The average experimentally measured stiffness was 300.8 N/m, with a standard deviation of 73.4. This results in a coefficient of variation of 0.244, which is a relatively high value and demonstrates the variation in mechanical performance for bamboo, even in culms of the same species and roughly similar size. Of the two sets of model results, the Non-Concentric based model is more accurate to the experimental data with an average 11.8% difference in calculated stiffness, whereas the prism based models have an average difference of 21.1%. Whilst the average percentage difference is significantly different between the two models, the averages are somewhat skewed due to outliers where the prism model is very poor, specifically culms 4, 5, 6 and 7. This correlates to culms which had noticeably larger variations in their geometry, and underlies the increased importance of the higher fidelity representation when the culms themselves have more variation.

Figure 6: Load Vs Displacement for Bamboo Culms Comparison of NCC Based FEA, Prismatic Based FEA and Experimental Results

Figure 7: Calculated bending stiffness of culms and models alongside percentage differences between FEA and experiments.

An area where the non-concentric circle culm model may carry a significant benefit is in the prediction of failure loads and damage onset. The irregular geometry of bamboo culms may lead to stress concentrations developing at certain areas on the surface of the culm such as the nodes. These stress concentrations may then lead to failure onset such as a crack forming at that area. The geometry produced via the Non-concentric circle culm model will be able to more accurately determine the locations of such stress when compared to a prismatic model. This can be shown through a comparison of the modelled FEA stress maps shown in Figure 8 where the Non-Concentric circle FEA model also predicts a stress concentration at the node location. In the prismatic model the stress is evenly and symmetrically distributed across the surface and the peak value is slightly lower than what is present in the Non-Concentric circle FEA model. In order to validate this against experimental results, testing to failure would be required. This was not done as a part of these tests and exploration of this aspect of performance is left to future work.

Figure 8: Stress maps from non-concentric circle and prismatic tube FEA models for Culm 5.

4 BAMBOO WRAPTOR TRUSS FEA MODELLING AND VALIDATION

WrapToR trusses have also been manufactured from bamboo culms. These trusses have been manufactured using flax fibre tow wetted out with epoxy resin for the shear members. An example of a manufactured truss is shown in Figure 9. WrapToR trusses are defined by as set of parameters which describe the geometry of each truss. These are labelled on Figure 9 and are described in

Table 1. The WrapToR geometry used for the trusses in this investigation are also shown in Table 1 and each truss was manufactured to these specifications.

Figure 9: Wound Bamboo/Flax WrapToR truss with labelled geometric parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Description	Value Used
Centre to centre distance	CtC	Distance between the centre of the chord member cross sections.	160 mm
Winding angle	θ	Angle between shear member and chord member.	45°
Truss Length	L	Length of truss beam.	1 m
Chord member diameter	d_c	Diameter of the chord member used.	Varies between 22mm and 26 mm
Shear member diameter	d_s	Diameter of the wound composite tow which forms the shear web.	4 mm

Table 1: WrapToR geometry parameters and parameters used in manufactured trusses.

During the manufacture of these trusses the non-concentric circle culm model was used to modify the winding process to mitigate the impact of the geometry variation. Because variation in the culm can cause discrepancies in the winding path geometry, as shown in Figure 2, care needs to be taken in the positioning of the chord members on the winding mandrel to account for this. An adjustable mandrel which allows for the culms to be tilted along its length was designed and this was used alongside a companion tool for the WrapToR winding machine which uses the non-concentric culm model to optimise the initial position of the culm. The companion tool calculates the WrapToR node position based on the combination of culm rotation and mandrel tilt. This tool calculates every possible combination and returns the set of parameters which aligns closest with the projected WrapToR node positions if the chord members were prismatic. Such an approach is not possible with a lower fidelity representation of the culm geometry which demonstrates the value of the non-concentric circle culm model for WrapToR truss manufacture.

Similarly to the individual culm tests, each culm used in the trusses was scanned for the non-concentric circle culm model and thus FEA models of these trusses have been able to be produced. Again, both prismatic tube models and those based off the non-concentric circle culm model have been developed. The models developed here differ from those used in previous WrapToR studies in that they are produced with Abaqus rather than a bespoke Matlab code. Additionally, they represent the connection between the shear members and chord members in a different way. The MSA models used previously represent the geometry of the WrapToR joint through the use of an inextensible, shear

deformable element, which offsets the shear from the surface of the chord [6]. This element is useful as it is able to represent the shear deformations in the joint itself and allow for a more accurate representation of shear member length. Because we have an actual surface rather than the beam element in the MSA code, we can map the geometry of joint more accurately onto the chord member itself. The result is a model such as that shown in Figure 10. This provides an accurate model for shear member length which is its most important geometric property. Currently this connection is only representative, with kinematic ties connecting the chord and shear members but future work will include implementation of joint mechanics which can ideally model the interactions of the adhesive joint and help predict failure due to the bond failure, which is a common failure mode for WrapToR trusses [6].

Figure 10 WrapToR model in Abaqus with accurate geometry nodes and NCC based culms.

4.1 Model Validation

Results from the FEA analysis are compared to four-point bending experiments for six different truss beam specimens. Four-point bending was chosen over three-point bending in this case due to the low aspect ratio of the trusses which promotes a shear dominated response. Because a four-point test causes an area of no shear forces between the loading points the performance in bending can be solely assessed. Four-point bending also allows for the load to be distributed across two loading points which is useful in preventing early crack propagation in a brittle material such as bamboo. Each truss was tested to failure. The results of this testing and comparative modelled responses are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Results of Truss Testing

Figure 11 shows a nonlinear response in bending which is associated with the truss shear members buckling. Shear members buckling and subsequently snapping was the most common failure most observed in testing and the softening behaviour has been able to be captured by the FEA models which is a positive indication that the modelled response is accurate to the real response. Overall, the FEA models themselves are a good match to the experimental results and can predict the response of the tested trusses to a reasonable degree of accuracy. There does not appear to be a significant difference between the prismatic models and the models based on the non-concentric circle. The FEA modelled responses in the linear region seem to align very closely together which is due to the primary deformation in that region being linked to shear member deformations that are modelled very similarly between models. The tested trusses have an average initial linear stiffness of 7880 N/m with a standard deviation of 1452 N/m, resulting in a 0.1842 coefficient of variance. This is lower than the coefficient calculated from the individual culm tests, but is still high. It may be the case that the truss geometry has some moderating effect on the variance, as individual culm performance is bending dominated, whereas the culms within truss beams will generally be loaded in a more axial manner, and bending performance is more non-linear with geometry than axial performance, This inherent geometrical mitigation could be further enhanced with careful pre-selection of culms to balance out culm level variation at the truss beam level mechanical performance.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work presents the Non-concentric circle culm model as a measurement method and representation of bamboo culms. The model takes many measurements of the distance of the truss surface to a known reference point for and calculate a circle to represent that cross section. These circles are placed at a calculated centre based on the measurements taken which captures geometric features such as pre-bends in the culm. This model has been developed for the explicit purpose of aiding manufacture and performance predictions for bamboo based Wrapped Tow Reinforced trusses.

This method has demonstrated usefulness in the manufacture of WrapToR trusses by allowing for an optimisation of the position of chord members in the mandrel to provide an even tow path during winding, resulting in more uniform, higher quality manufacture. This is an important step in the development of Bamboo WrapToR trusses which may help address current challenges surrounding bamboo construction.

The models have also been used to produce finite element analysis models of individual culms and as part of FEA models for WrapToR trusses. In both cases model validation shows that there is a good match between the prediction of the FEA models and the experimentally gathered data. There is confidence that FEA models using the non-concentric circle culm model can be used to model bamboo culm performance. On average, the non-concentric circle culm model more closely aligns with the experimental data than modelling culms as a prism suggesting that it offers a slightly better method of approximating culm performance in bending. Given the significant variation in mechanical performance between culms and trusses, the non-concentric circle culm model can be useful to help predict variation and allow for a more informed design process to take place without the need for overly conservative estimations.

There are also some indications that the non-concentric circle FEA model may be able to identify areas where there are stress concentrations which could aid in failure prediction, but more comprehensive work to gather appropriate material properties, and improve the data collection for experiments must first take place.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) UK through: the Centre for Doctoral Training in Composites Science, Engineering and Manufacturing (CDT CoSEM; grant number EP/S021728/1) at the University of Bristol..

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